

DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE PARTNERSHIPS AS A FACTOR IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF TRAINING

¹Sultanova Muhabbat Shamsievna, ²Kultaeva Feruza Ergashovna

^{1,2} Senior teachers, Samarkand state architecture and civil engineering university

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Abstract. *The transformation of the economic structure, the emergence of labor markets, intellectual capital, educational services, have changed the strategy of personnel training. Due to the change in ownership forms and the sharp drop in industrial production, the traditional relationship between vocational schools and employers has been disrupted.*

Keywords: *education system, innovative projects, professional career, effective system, potentials of vocational education, method.*

New economic conditions dictate new approaches to interaction with labor market participants, focusing on the specific needs of employers, which become a tool for solving, first, the economic problems of society.

Being one of the most conservative, the education system is forced to adapt, constantly and timely change, cover an increasing number of stakeholders, strive to involve almost all possible resources.

The world community has already accumulated considerable experience of social interaction carried out through the partnership of its participants. Social partnership is recognized as the most important factor in the modernization of vocational education. Hence, there is a need to find partners with common production tasks and interests.

The mechanisms of interaction are based on certain fundamental principles and norms:

- a. Partnership relations are based on the voluntary recognition by partners of each other as participants in the relationship.
- b. The decisive factor in partnership relations is the mutual interest of the parties, respect and consideration of the interests of partners.
- c. Mutual responsibility for the common cause is assumed, the obligation to fulfill the agreements reached within the framework of agreements and contracts.

The requirements of the industry for the qualification and quality of training of specialists are growing.

The problems of today in the training of qualified specialists, I think:

- a. Material and technical support of the educational process; (for high-quality training, complex technological equipment of a new generation is necessary)
- b. Personnel "hunger"; (lack of teaching staff with innovative thinking)
- c. Motivation of students. (Low social level of working specialties)

Since the approaches to solving these problems are different, conditionally, partnerships can be divided into two categories:

- Partners in the labor market;
- Partners in the educational services market.

A common task in this cooperation is the training of highly qualified personnel. Pursuing a policy of global modernization of production, they are forced to look for specialists for complex technological equipment. Today, having a modern training center, we have something to offer our

partner.

They once support us in innovative projects and in solving some social problems. The provision of jobs with high-tech equipment, participation in the technological process of the enterprise during industrial practice increases the degree of responsibility among students, assumes a higher quality level of training, increases the competitiveness of our graduate.

Scientific and technological progress leads to the emergence of new tools and objects of labor, new production and information technologies. The use of innovative methods in pedagogical practice allows us to bring the quality of specialist training to a new level.

The participation of the school staff in the priority national project "Education" was an incentive to create a system of work to improve professional competencies and develop a quality assessment system.

Now on the last issue in my report - the issue of motivation to learn.

The low social bar makes working professions unattractive; therefore, it is necessary to develop interest in obtaining vocational education through strong incentives. We have followed the path of building a professional career trajectory.

In modern conditions, I think this is continuous education. Its task is to create an effective system of combining the potentials of vocational education institutions and enterprises for the training of technical and engineering personnel.

The quality and expected effectiveness of the presented innovative educational program; the current state of the quality of the training of workers and specialists and the interaction of the educational institution with employers; co-financing of the training of workers and specialists for high-tech industries, including for solving urgent tasks of priority national projects.

The effectiveness of contractual relations with employers on the provision of modern practice bases, places for practical training and industrial training, as well as places for internships of teaching staff and Master of Industrial Training; employers' participation in the educational process, assessment of the quality of graduate training (final certification).

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